

Isolation and characterization of squalene extracted from the processing waste of freshwater fish species

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Abstract

Squalene (C₃₀H₅₀) is a natural, highly unsaturated terpenoid hydrocarbon found in animals, plants, and humans, notable for its applications in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and nutraceuticals. Squalene is a bioactive functional lipid that has antioxidant, anticancer, and cardioprotective properties. The present study aimed to extract and purify squalene from the waste of the fish processing and value addition unit. The fisheries industry may have a great impact on addressing poverty and improving the economy of a country. Almost 35-40% of edible fish meat is produced by fish processing, which can be utilized for the production of different products. Our study was planned to extract and purify squalene from different sources by using the method of fractional crystallization to achieve the best yields at the lowest possible cost. The qualitative and quantitative analyses were done on gas chromatography-mass spectrometry to check the purity of squalene. Squalene found its applications in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and nutraceuticals. It was originally extracted from shark liver oil but is easily present in animals, plants, and microorganisms. The richest source of squalene is the shark liver among all available natural sources. Notably, the head portion of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) yielded squalene with a purity of 97%, highlighting its potential as a viable renewable source. Sustainable management of fish waste can result in the recovery of several bioactive substances.

Keywords: Squalene, Bioactive substances, Shark liver, Extraction, Renewable sources

Introduction

The fisheries industry plays a crucial role in poverty alleviation and economic strengthening on both micro and macro scales. During the last two decades, the demand for processed fish products has increased in Pakistan. By exporting more fish and value-added products, Pakistan can improve its economy (Mohsin et al., 2015). Fish processing comprises many stages from the time of harvest till the supply of value-added products. Removal of head, washing, removal of scales, gut removal, and removal of fins are the main phases to process the fish (Caruso, 2015). Presently, a variety of freshwater fish species are cultured in more than 50,000 acres of land in the province (FAO, 2011). According to a calculation, the per capita intake of fish is 20.2 kg per year, and its intake is increasing day by day (FAO, 2018). Several freshwater fish species have been presented by Pakistan as yield improvement. It may include rohu (*Labeo rohita*), mrigal (*Cirrhinus mrigala*), common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*), grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*), and bighead carp (*Hypophthalmichthys nobilis*) (Karim et al., 2016). It is critical to process and preserve the fish from spoilage due to the higher content of PUFA and water in the fish (Nahid et al., 2016). Throughout the fish processing, a huge quantity of total fish waste, wastewater, and solid waste is produced (Rebah and Miled, 2013). Fish waste, on average, consists of liver (5%), backbone (14%), head (21%), lungs (10%), and fins (10%) (Ghaly et al., 2013). It is predictable that about 25% of the produced fish is considered as fish waste and about 75% is used for human consumption worldwide (Rebah and Miled, 2013). Almost 35-40% of edible meat is produced by fish processing, which can be utilized for the production of different products (Suresh et al., 2018). Every year, 18-30 million tons of fish processing waste are discarded in the world (Kunwar et al., 2022).

Sustainable management of fish waste could result in the recovery of several bioactive substances such as fatty acids, amino acids, sterols, lipids, and oils (Gomez et al., 2020). Fish oil comprises a healthy quantity of beneficial components such as Omega-3, Omega-6, and Omega

9 and squalene, which are very good for health (Hadinoto et al., 2020). Pakistan export of fishery products stand at about 0.25% of world export. A rough estimate based on maximum sustainable yield is from coastal areas in the form of value-added products. The carp is an important source of fish meat in Pakistan and neighboring countries. Indian major carps, including Rohu (*Labeo rohita*), Mori (*Cirrhinus mrigala*), and Thaila (*Catla catla*) are considered a potential source of protein in Pakistan. These carps are considered high-value commercial fish species and are being cultured on priority by local farmers (Sheikh et al., 2017).

The fish liver oil industry is smaller than the fish body oil industry. For oil extraction, two main fish species whose livers are commonly used are shark and cod. The fishery industry provides byproducts in the form of squalene from shark liver and cod liver oil for human consumption (Fandino et al., 2005). Shark liver oil mainly consists of hydrocarbons. Squalene made up about 90% of the shark liver (Heller et al., 1957). Hydrocarbons in the body oils of other fish species (Herring) have been found at around 0.05% (Kinsella, 2020). Commercial fish oil has been found to contain hydrocarbons less than 0.2% (Young, 1986). Squalene is a highly unsaturated hydrocarbon, which is present in animals, plants, and humans as a natural lipid (Nenadis and Tsimidou, 2002). Squalene is pale yellow in appearance, and its melting and boiling points are 70°C and 285°C (Ortega et al., 2012). Olive oil, rice bran oil, amaranth oil, wheat germ oil, and shark liver oil are the natural sources of squalene (Fornari et al., 2008). Squalene is abundantly present in nature, such as in higher plants (Liu et al., 1976) and in fungi (Senbagalakshmi et al., 2019). Squalene in the range of 0.01-0.4 percent is present in commercial oils like rice bran, peanut, sunflower, and corn (Ko et al., 2002). It is considered that the richest source of squalene is olive oil, which has squalene in the range of 112-869 mg per 100 grams (Ostlund et al., 2002). Another higher content of squalene is also present in Amaranth seed oil. It has squalene in the range of 2-7 percent (Berger et al., 2003). Squalene is a linear triterpene that is available at high purity greater than 98%. Apart from animal sources, squalene can also be extracted from plant sources such as sesame seeds, soybean oils, and grapeseed, which contain a mixture of hydrocarbons (Hardy and Puzovic, 2009). Squalene has moisturizing, emollient, and antioxidant effects (Kim et al., 2012). It has been widely used in different industries, including cosmetics, vaccines, and functional foods (Lekshmi et al., 2019). It has been extensively used in human vaccines as an adjuvant and produces antibodies against antigens in Gulf War syndrome (Asa et al., 2002).

Squalene is an unsaturated hydrocarbon (Kraujalis et al., 2013). It is a precursor during the biosynthesis of all steroids (He et al., 2002). Apart from animal sources, the vegetable sources of squalene are amaranth oil (6.0%-8.0%) and olive oil (0.1%-0.7%) (Shin et al., 2004). Human

sebum contains 13% of squalene, and it plays an important role as a protection against UV-associated skin damage (Spanova and Daum, 2011). It is considered that the richest source of squalene is the shark liver among all the available natural sources (Popa et al., 2015). Shark liver has 79 to 88% oil content, which is a high range of oil content (Norhidayah et al., 2012). Besides sharks, some other marine and freshwater species also contain squalene. In these fish, the content of squalene depends on their net weight, such as 70-1803 mg per kg (Kopicova and Vavreinova, 2007; Bavisetty and Narayan, 2015). On average, the content of squalene in the muscular fat of individual fish is 98 to 1536 mg per kg. Although the content of squalene in visceral fat is about 70 to 1803.8 mg per kg. Fish processing by-products also have a significant amount of squalene, mainly in the fish liver (Bavisetty and Narayan, 2015).

Squalene has a wide range of applications in medicines, food additives, cosmetics, and nutraceuticals. It can assist as a lubricant at low temperatures (Spanova and Daum, 2011; Kim and Karadeniz, 2012; Bindu et al., 2015). It also has applications in the drug transfer system, such as vaccines in the form of squalene-based emulsion. Squalene-based emulsions are commonly used due to their stability and biocompatibility properties (Reddy and Couvreur, 2009). Squalene also acts as a skin and eye antioxidant, antibacterial, and antifungal, which is generally used in the cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries (Vazquez et al., 2007). Squalene is an effective carrier for the distribution of orally administered drugs. It plays an important role in the formation of bile acids because it is easily absorbed and transported to the liver (Gracia et al., 2019). It is considered that one of the best disease control measures is vaccination for good farming practices (Secombes, 2008; Adelman et al., 2008). Numerous vaccines have been established, but a harmless and cost-effective vaccine is anticipated (Nishizawa, 2011). Squalene could decrease the risk of some types of pancreatic and breast cancer. The side effects of chemotherapy, such as toxicity and DNA damage, can be reduced by the use of squalene in chemotherapy (Pacetti et al., 2019).

Squalene oil has application in the area of food science as a bioactive compound. It has wide range of health-promoting properties. It acts as a biofunctional lipid compound (Kim and Karadeniz, 2012). Squalene promotes various health benefits beyond the nutritional values. Mo et al. (2018) described that fish waste has been used to generate value-added products such as fish oil, bioactive peptides, amino acids, fish protein, collagen, and gelatin. These products have being utilized in the production of animal feed, biogas, enzyme separation, natural pigment, and food packaging. Production of by-products from fish waste has become an advantageous and trending concept.

Fish oil has been extracted, cleaned, and purified from the waste of the fishing industry for the development of different compounds (Ray et al., 2016). Zhang et al. (2022) performed a study on the characterization of seed oil. They studied the antioxidant activity, thermal and rheological properties, fatty acid analysis, squalene, phytosterols, tocopherols and total phenolic content of the seed oil. They concluded that seed oil has a content of squalene in the range of 96.78 mg per kg, phytosterol in the range of 119.6 mg per kg and tocopherols in the range of 42.01 mg per kg. First-time squalene was extracted from the liver of a shark in the form of oil. Later on, it was also discovered in microorganisms, plants and animals. The purpose of our study is to develop a simple and rapid method for the extraction and purification of squalene from freshwater fish species. This strategy to use leftover processing discards is one step towards sustainability and protection of marine life. With shark fishing restrictions to protect marine biodiversity, alternative renewable sources for squalene extraction are essential.

Materials and methods

Experimental site

The present study was conducted at the fish processing and value addition unit, Department of Fisheries and Aquaculture, the University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Lahore, Ravi campus, Pattoki.

Sample collection

Fish processing waste containing the samples of Liver, Head and Processed Combined Waste was collected from fish processing and value addition unit. Immediately fish samples were stored at -20°C until processing. A total of ten kg samples were collected to ensure statistical relevance, stored immediately at -20°C to preserve integrity. Samples were washed with distilled water to remove debris. Fish samples were autoclaved to make them free of pathogens.

Fish Species

The freshwater fish species including *Labeo rohita*, *Cirrhinus mrigala* and *Cyprinus carpio* were randomly selected. The mean total length was 43.80cm and weight was around 2 kg. Fish samples were kept in ice boxes and transported to Food Chemistry, Central Laboratory Complex for oil extraction.

Sample preparation

Sample was prepared by the formation of homogenate of each sample separately. Homogenizing mixture of each sample was made by using different parts such as liver, head, and processed combined waste of individual fish separately. Three different sample preparations were made. Each sample was grinded separately in a mixer blender. Lab homogenizer was used for sample

preparation. Homogenized fish samples were stored in the refrigerator (-4°C) (Kopicovaz & Vavreinova, 2007).

Extraction of oil from fish samples

Extraction of oil was done after homogenizing the body parts separately in a mixer blender. For the extraction of oil five grams of each sample was taken in conical flask. 10 ml of chloroform and 20 ml of methanol was added to the conical flask. This mixture was vortex for 2 min at 681 rpm. After that 10 ml of chloroform was added and mixed vigorously for 2 minutes. Distilled water (18 ml) was added to the mixture after 2 min. It was again vortexed for two minutes. Centrifugation was done to separate the layers at 2000 rpm for 10 minutes. After centrifugation two layers were formed and were separate out. The lower layer was transferred to flask by using Pasteur pipette. After that a second extraction was done. For second extraction 20 ml of 10 percent volume by volume methanol was taken in chloroform and was vortex for two minutes. The chloroform phase was added to the first extract after centrifugation. At 45°C evaporation was done in rotary evaporator (Bligh & Dyer, 1959). The residue was further dried at 90°C for eighty minutes in an oven (Kopicovaz & Vavreinova, 2007).

Characterization of oil

Fish oil extracted from three different sources (Liver, Head and Combined Fish Processing Waste) was characterized (AOCS, 1995).

Fatty acid analysis

Fatty acid content of the oil obtained from three different sources was determined (AOAC, 2011). Lipids were extracted from three different sources. Fatty acid methyl esters were prepared by the addition of 1.5 ml of 0.5 M sodium hydroxide in methanol for 25 mg of lipids. This mixture was heated at a temperature of 100 °C for 2 minutes in a boiling water bath. After heating for 2 minutes, it was cooled. In the next step, we added 2 ml of 14 percent boron trifluoride in methanol. It was heated again for 30 minutes in a water bath, and 1 ml of isooctane was added. 5 ml of saturated NaCl was added for the separation of isooctane and methanol. In a separate tube, we collected the isooctane. This process was repeated one more time. In the next step, nitrogen gas was used, and 2 mL of isooctane was dried at room temperature. GC-MS (7890B, Agilent Technologies), along with a flame ionization detector, was used for the analysis of fatty acid methyl esters. For GC-MS, the temperature of the injector and detector was set at 260 °C, and the temperature of the fused silica capillary column was 140-240 °C. During the experiment, helium gas was flowed at 0.9 ml per minute. It was used as a carrier gas. Identification of the fatty acids

was done on the base of retention time and was compared with the standard. Absolute response was determined by the peaks of each fatty acid (Folch et al., 1957).

Tocopherols analysis

Tocopherols were analyzed on HPLC equipped with a UV-DAAD fluorescence detector, and a C 18 controller (1260 Infinity II, Agilent Technologies). One gram of oil sample was weighed and added in a 10 ml volumetric flask, n-hexane was added, and the mixture was diluted up to the mark. Excitation wavelength and emission wavelength were set at 290 nm and 330 nm. Standard tocopherols were used, and calibration curves were made, followed by Koprivnjak et al. (2008).

Phenols analysis

The phenol content of oil samples was determined according to the procedure reported by Agidew et al. (2021). Briefly (2g) oil sample was mixed with 3.75 ml of 7% NaCo₃ and 0.75 Folin reagent. The mixture was incubated in dark conditions, and after 30 minutes, absorbance was measured on a UV-VIS spectrophotometer at 750 nm.

Purification of squalene

Fractional crystallization was done for the purification of squalene from the extracted oil. It was done by dissolving 500 µl of the extracted oil in 2 ml of absolute ethanol. To completely homogenize the mixture, it was vortexed for one minute. The homogenized mixture was kept at ambient temperature for six hours for gravity separation. Supernatant was collected after gravity separation. Squalene content was determined by HPLC. Twenty microliters of ethanolic extract were dissolved in 500 microliters of mobile phase, which was 100 percent acetonitrile. The RP-HPLC method was used for further analysis (Patel et al., 2020). For the purification of samples, the temperature of the column was kept at 35 °C. Volume of the injection was 30µl for sample analysis. The flow rate of the mobile phase was 1.5 ml per minute by using 100 percent acetonitrile in an isocratic mode. The duration of the program was 30 minutes. A diode array detector was used to check the analytes. Wavelength of the detector was set at 195 nm for the analysis of samples Bavisetty & Narayan (2015). GC- MS (7890B, Agilent Technologies) was used to check the purity of extracted squalene (Ardhyni et al., 2022).

Peroxide Value and Acid Value

Peroxide value was determined according to official (AOCS, 1995) standards. One ml of squalene was dissolved in 6 ml of acetic acid and chloroform solution in a 3:2 ratio. From this solution, 0.1 ml saturated squalene was added to the solution and was shaken for 1 minute. The solution was titrated with 0.1 N sodium thiosulfate until the disappearance of coloration. The process was repeated with the starch solution until the color disappeared. The value was expressed as

milliequivalents peroxide/1000 g per sample. The acid value was determined using the AOCS (1995) standard methods.

Statistical analysis

A two-way ANOVA was employed to evaluate the influence of categorical variables on dependent variables, followed by Tukey's HSD test to assess pairwise differences, with significance set at $p < 0.05$ (Steel et al., 1996).

Results

Concentration of squalene and sterols

The content of squalene and sterol in different parts of freshwater fish species is mentioned in Table 1. In *Labeo rohita*, the content of squalene in all analyzed parts ranged from 1.00 to 3.02 g/100g. Combined waste (3.02 ± 0.26 g/100g) was the most abundant source of squalene in *Labeo rohita*. In *Cirrhinus mrigala*, the content of squalene in all analyzed parts ranged from 1.65 to 2.00 g/100g. Combined waste (2.00 ± 0.04 g/100g) was the most abundant source of squalene in *Cirrhinus mrigala*. Sterols exist in four different forms. Brassicasterol was not detected in any fish part if any fish species. Campesterol existed in the range of 40-43 in different parts of *Labeo rohita*. Campesterol existed in the range of 41-44 in different parts of *Cyprinus carpio*. Campesterol existed in the range of 39-41 in different parts of *Cirrhinus mrigala*. Stigmasterol content was higher in *Cyprinus carpio* (44.09). β -Sitosterol content existed in the range of 76-79 in different parts of *Labeo rohita*..

Table 1. Concentration of squalene and sterols in different parts of freshwater fish species

Fish species	Sample	Squalene	Brassicasterol	Campesterol	Stigmasterol	β -Sitost
<i>Labeo rohita</i>	Head	1.00 ± 0.02^c	N.D.	40.5 ± 0.09^c	39.01 ± 1.03^c	76.03 ± 2
	Liver	2.24 ± 0.03^b	N.D.	42.03 ± 0.07^b	41.08 ± 1.00^b	78.09 ± 1
	Combined waste	3.02 ± 0.26^a	N.D.	43.09 ± 0.05^a	42.06 ± 0.03^a	79.65 ± 2
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	Head	3.06 ± 0.76^b	N.D.	42.06 ± 0.03^b	44.09 ± 0.98^a	80.08 ± 3
	Liver	2.65 ± 0.45^c	N.D.	41.00 ± 1.00^c	42.03 ± 0.07^c	77.09 ± 2
	Combined waste	3.76 ± 0.98^a	N.D.	44.09 ± 0.98^a	43.09 ± 0.05^b	78.09 ± 1
<i>Cirrhinus mrigala</i>	Head	1.65 ± 0.04^c	N.D.	40.09 ± 0.01^b	39.09 ± 1.00^c	75.09 ± 2
	Liver	1.98 ± 0.05^b	N.D.	39.02 ± 0.01^c	41.00 ± 1.00^a	74.00 ± 1

Combined waste	2.00±0.04 ^a	N.D.	41.09±0.02 ^a	40.07±1.00 ^b	73.07±2
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Concentration of Tocopherol and Phenol

Phenol content present in different parts of freshwater fish species has been illustrated in Table 2. Total phenol content of *Labeo rohita* was 163.77 (mg/kg), which was higher compared to that found in *Cyprinus carpio* (102.93 mg/kg) and *Cirrhinus mrigala* (95.83 g/kg). The content of tocopherols in *Cyprinus carpio* was 370.89 (mg/kg), which was higher than that found in *Labeo rohita* (354.23 mg/kg) and *Cirrhinus mrigala* (343.65 mg/kg).

Table 2. Concentration of Tocopherol and Phenol in different freshwater fish species

<i>Labeo rohita</i>	<i>Cirrhinus mrigala</i>	<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	
α-tocopherol (mg/kg)	338.73±5.86 ^b	320.83±7.80 ^c	357.83±4.33 ^a
β- tocopherol (mg/kg)	1.34±0.04 ^c	3.93±0.69 ^a	2.73±0.01 ^b
γ- tocopherol (mg/kg)	12.83±1.01 ^a	5.83±0.43 ^c	9.33±0.51 ^b
Total tocopherol (mg/kg)	354.23±7.22 ^b	343±6.75 ^c	370.89±7.57 ^a
Total phenols (mg/kg)	163.77±6.54 ^a	95.83±3.86 ^c	102.93±6.86 ^b

Fatty Acid composition of freshwater fish species

The fish oil fatty acid composition for different parts of freshwater fish species is summarized in Table 3). A significant portion of fatty acids was unsaturated fatty acids. In the present study, unsaturated fatty acid content (29-33%) was higher in *Labeo rohita* compared to the other two species. Saturated fatty acid content was higher in *Cirrhinus mrigala*. Palmitic acid was higher in the head region of *Cirrhinus mrigala*. It was in the range of 13.5±0.03. Margaric acid was 3.05±0.01 in the liver of both *Cyprinus carpio* and *Labeo rohita*. Lauric acid was found in higher amounts in the head region of *Cyprinus carpio*. It was found in the range of 6.00±0.02. Capric acid was higher in the liver of *Cirrhinus mrigala*. It was in the range of 2.66 ± 0.09. The amount of oleic acid was the same in the head region of all the fish samples. It was in the range of 3.11±0.05. But the amount was different in other parts of all the samples.

Table 3. Fatty acid analysis of freshwater fish species

	Species								
	<i>Labeo rohita</i>			<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>			<i>Cirrhinus mrigala</i>		
	Head	Liver	Combined Waste	Head	Liver	Combined Waste	Head	Liver	Combined Waste
Myristic acid	6.30 ±0.11 ^a	3.30 ±0.11 ^d	5.45 ±0.02 ^b	5.30 ±0.11 ^b	2.30 ±0.11 ^c	5.05 ±0.02 ^b	4.40 ±0.31 ^c	3.34 ±0.11 ^d	4.30 ±0.11 ^c
Palmitoleic acid	1.23± 0.02 ^b	1.18± 0.04 ^c	1.11± 0.02 ^c	1.13± 0.03 ^c	1.11± 0.01 ^c	1.21± 0.02 ^b	2.23± 0.01 ^a	1.09± 0.04 ^d	0.71± 0.02 ^c
Palmitic acid	12.5±0.04 ^b	6.56±0.04 ^c	10.5±0.03 ^c	12.5±0.04 ^b	7.56±0.04 ^d	10.2±0.03 ^c	13.5±0.03 ^a	5.10±0.04 ^f	7.5±0.03 ^d
Margaric acid	2.05±0.01 ^b	3.05±0.01 ^a	3.00±0.01 ^a	2.00±0.01 ^b	3.05±0.01 ^a	3.00±0.01 ^a	3.33±0.01 ^a	2.10±0.01 ^b	1.88±0.01 ^c
Stearic acid	4.65±0.05 ^a	0.75±0.05 ^d	3.55±0.05 ^b	4.05±0.05 ^a	0.75±0.01 ^d	3.55±0.01 ^b	2.65±0.05 ^c	0.55±0.05 ^d	2.35±0.09 ^c
Arachidic acid	1.44±0.03 ^c	1.99±0.04 ^b	2.01±0.00 ^a	1.44±0.03 ^c	2.99±0.04 ^a	-	1.44±0.03 ^c	2.09±0.04 ^a	-
Linolenic acid	3.06±0.20 ^a	-	2.1±1.15 ^b	3.06±0.20 ^b	3.14±0.10 ^b	2.59±0.01 ^c	3.06±0.20 ^b	-	1.76±0.02 ^d
Tricosanoic acid	2.02±0.16 ^a	3.44±0.15 ^a	0.75±0.05 ^c	1.02±0.16 ^d	3.49±0.15 ^a	2.1±1.14 ^b	1.72±0.16 ^c	1.45±0.15 ^c	2.03±1.00 ^b
		0.05±0.11 ^c		0.75±0.11 ^c	1.05±0.11 ^b	0.77±0.15 ^c	0.65±0.11 ^d	1.07±0.11 ^b	0.55±0.02 ^c
∑SFA	22.75±0.11^c	19.11±0.5^d	20.05±0.2^d	31.44±0.11^a	24.75±1.11^b	18.55±0.01 ^c	30.65±2.20 ^b	17.10±0.04 ^c	16.99±0.09 ^f
Lauric acid	5.65±0.02 ^b	3.65±0.04 ^c	5.75±0.02 ^b	6.00±0.02 ^a	3.65±0.20 ^c	5.85±0.04 ^b	5.35±0.02 ^b	1.65±0.04 ^d	5.25±0.02 ^b
Capric acid	2.10±0.09 ^b	1.96±0.09 ^c	2.99±0.09 ^a	2.80±0.09 ^a	1.85±0.09 ^c	2.10±0.03 ^b	2.00±0.09 ^b	2.66±0.09 ^a	1.75±0.09 ^d
Caprylic acid	3.75±0.2 ^a	3.71±0.21 ^a	2.15±0.21 ^c	2.75±0.21 ^b	3.11±0.21 ^a	2.79±0.20 ^b	2.75±0.21 ^b	3.62±0.21 ^a	2.15±0.21 ^b
Caproic acid	4.76±0.02 ^f	11.5±0.32 ^c	18.5±0.02 ^c	19.5±0.32 ^b	12.5±0.32 ^c	22.5±0.33 ^a	20.5±0.32 ^b	11.5±0.32 ^c	16.5±0.02 ^d
Carboeric acid	3.52±0.54 ^a	2.00±0.01 ^b	2.75±0.06 ^b	1.75±0.06 ^c	2.00±0.01 ^b	1.75±0.06 ^c	1.75±0.06 ^c	2.00±0.01 ^b	2.77±0.06 ^b
∑MUFA	18.67±0.02^b	21.21±0.04^b	31,56±0.21^c	30.98±0.08^c	23.32±0.02^f	34.75±0.33^a	32.87±0.75^b	20.98±0.32^c	28.09±0.02^d
Oleic acid	3.11±0.05 ^b	3.01±0.05 ^c	3.03±0.05 ^c	3.18±0.05 ^b	3.19±0.05 ^b	3.03±0.01 ^c	3.41±0.05 ^a	3.01±0.05 ^d	3.03±0.05 ^c
Elaidic acid	1.12±0.9 ^c	2.06±0.09 ^a	1.32±0.09 ^b	2.12±0.09 ^a	2.00±0.09 ^a	1.33±0.09 ^b	1.12±0.09 ^c	2.06±0.09 ^a	1.32±0.09 ^b
Erucic acid	2.75±0.0 ^c	3.31±0.03 ^a	2.05±0.03 ^d	2.65±0.03 ^c	3.21±0.03 ^a	2.55±0.03 ^c	1.75±0.03 ^c	3.91±0.03 ^a	3.05±0.03 ^b
Nervonic acid	3.05±0.01 ^a	1.55±0.21 ^c	2.31±0.21 ^b	3.55±0.20 ^a	1.25±0.01 ^d	2.21±0.01 ^b	2.55±0.21 ^b	1.55±0.21 ^c	2.31±0.21 ^b
Gadoleic acid	2.98±0.9 ^a	0.95±0.02 ^c	1.30±0.01 ^b	0.98±0.03 ^c	0.05±0.03 ^c	1.20±0.01 ^b	0.99±0.01 ^c	0.55±0.02 ^d	2.30±0.01 ^a
∑PUFA	13.05±0.9^a	11.05±0.05^b	10.65±0.03^c	12.33±0.03^b	9.98±0.05^d	8.99±0.21^d	7.98±0.01^c	10.55±0.99^c	12.09±0.98^b

SFA=Saturated fatty acid, MUFA=Monounsaturated fatty acid, PUFA= Polyunsaturated fatty acid, (-) = Not Detected

Extraction and purification:

Squalene was extracted from different parts, such as liver, head, and the combined waste of freshwater fish species. Crude extract had an appearance of dry and blackish green appearance. It was sticky in nature. The HPLC technique was used for the determination of squalene. Fractional crystallization was done for the purification of squalene. Absolute ethanol was used in this technique to separate the compound. A mixture of acetone and methanol (3:7 vol/vol) was used in fractional crystallization. This method successfully separates the desired compounds from fish samples. The percentage purity of squalene obtained by the utilization of different parts of freshwater fish species has been illustrated in Fig. 1. The maximum purity of squalene was detected in the head portion of freshwater fish species. The highest purity (97%) of squalene was detected in the head portion of *Cyprinus carpio*. It was the highest % when compared to other ratios. *Cirrhinus mrigala* has 95%, and *Labeo rohita* has 96% purity of squalene in the head portion.

Figure 1. Percentage purity of Squalene extracted from freshwater fish species. Fig (a) (Part-wise comparison) Fig (b) (Species-wise comparison). The highest purity (97%) of squalene was detected in the head portion of *Cyprinus carpio*. It was the highest % when compared to other ratios. *Cirrhinus mrigala* has 95%, and *Labeo rohita* has 96% purity of squalene in the head portion.

Content of squalene

The content of squalene in different parts of freshwater fish species such as *Labeo rohita*, *Cirrhinus mrigala*, and *Cyprinus carpio* has been illustrated in (Fig. 2). In *Labeo rohita* the content of squalene in all analyzed parts ranged from 1.00 to 3.02 g/100g. Combined waste (3.02±0.26 g/100g) was the most abundant source of squalene in *Labeo rohita*. In *Cyprinus carpio*, the content of squalene in all analyzed

parts ranged from 2.65 to 3.76g/100g. In *Cirrhinus mrigala*, the content of squalene in all analyzed parts ranged from 1.65 to 2.00 g/100g. The content of squalene in the liver of *Cirrhinus mrigala* was 1.65 ± 0.04 . Content of squalene in the head region of *Cirrhinus mrigala* was $1.98.00\pm 0.05$.

Figure 2. Yield of squalene in different parts and species of freshwater fish. The content of squalene in the liver of *Cirrhinus mrigala* was 1.65 ± 0.04 . Content of squalene in the head region of *Cirrhinus mrigala* was $1.98.00\pm 0.05$.

Properties of squalene

Some properties of squalene, such as molecular weight, melting point, viscosity, boiling point, iodine number, and refractive index, are summarized. The boiling point was $284\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, a value that depends on the length of the carbon chain in oils. Molecular weight was $408.7\text{ g}07\text{g mol}^{-1}$ and viscosity was 12. All of these values meet the specified quality standards.

Table 4. Quality assessment of squalene

Properties	Value
Colour	Transparent
Molecular weight	408.07g mol^{-1}
Melting point	-73°C
Refractive index	1.434
Viscosity at 25°C	12
Density	0.867g/mL
Boiling point at 25°C	284°C
Iodine number	$380\text{g}/100\text{g}$

Acid values and peroxide values of the squalene

Acid values and peroxide values of the squalene extracted from freshwater fish species are shown in Fig 3. The acid values of *Labeo rohita*, *Cirrhinus mrigala*, and *Cyprinus carpio* were 28.43, 30.18, and 31.11 (mg KOH/g), respectively. Peroxide values of the above species were 7.99, 7.76, and 8.67 (mEQ/L). The variations that exist among all freshwater fish species depend upon the non-homogeneous nature of fish processing waste, different batches of fish, and the physiological variations of fishes.

Figure 3. Acid values and peroxide values of the squalene extracted from freshwater fish species. The acid values of *Labeo rohita*, *Cirrhinus mrigala*, and *Cyprinus carpio* were 28.43, 30.18, and 31.11 (mg KOH/g), respectively. Peroxide values of the above species were 7.99, 7.76, and 8.67 (mEQ/L).

Discussion

As shown in Table 1 and Fig 2, the amount of squalene in different parts of freshwater fish species has been mentioned. In *Labeo rohita*, the content of squalene in all analyzed parts ranged from 1.00 to 3.02 g/100g. Combined waste (3.02 ± 0.26 g/100g) was the most abundant source of squalene in *Labeo rohita*. Our findings relate to the results of Cicero et al. (2018), which were observed in mackerel processing waste. The content of squalene in the liver of *Labeo rohita* was 1.00 ± 0.02 (Zhang et al., 2020). Content of squalene in the head region of *Labeo rohita* was $2.24.00 \pm 0.03$. In *Cyprinus carpio*, the content of squalene in all analyzed parts ranged from 2.65 to 3.76g/100g. Combined waste (3.76 ± 0.98 g/100g) was the most abundant source of squalene in *Cyprinus carpio*. The content of squalene in the liver of *Cyprinus carpio* was

3.06±0.76. Content of squalene in the head region of *Cyprinus carpio* was 2.65.0±0.45. Our findings relate with the results of (Xiao et al., 2016), which were observed in olive oil squalene. In *Cirrhinus mrigala*, the content of squalene in all analyzed parts ranged from 1.65 to 2.00 g/100g. Combined waste (2.00±0.04 g/100g) was the most abundant source of squalene in *Cirrhinus mrigala*. The content of squalene in the liver of *Cirrhinus mrigala* was 1.65±0.04. Content of squalene in the head region of *Cirrhinus mrigala* was 1.98.00±0.05. Olive oil has squalene content in the range of 92-96 mg/100g (Cicero et al., 2018) but it was higher compared to that found in palm oil (52-58 mg/100g) and peanut oil (20-22 mg/100g) (Tan et al., 2007). Sterols exist in four different forms. Brassicasterol was not detected in any fish part of any fish species. Campesterol existed in the range of 40-43 in different parts of *Labeo rohita*. Campesterol existed in the range of 41-44 in different parts of *Cyprinus carpio*. Campesterol existed in the range of 39-41 in different parts of *Cirrhinus mrigala*. Stigmasterol content was higher in *Cyprinus carpio* (44.09). β -Sitosterol content existed in the range of 76-79 in different parts of *Labeo rohita* (Gao et al., 2018). β -Sitosterol content existed in the range of 77-80 in different parts of *Cyprinus carpio*. β -Sitosterol content existed in the range of 73-75 in different parts of *Cirrhinus mrigala*. Our findings agree with the results of (Gao et al., 2018), which were observed in cold-pressed oils.

Minor compounds such as phenol and tocopherol play a significant role in providing several health benefits to consumers (Santos et al., 2018). Phenol content present in different parts of freshwater fish species has been illustrated in Table 2. Total phenol content of *Labeo rohita* was 163.77 (mg/kg), which was higher compared to that found in *Cyprinus carpio* (102.93 mg/kg) and *Cirrhinus mrigala* (95.83 g/kg). Our findings relate to the findings of Yang et al. (2022), which were observed in peanut oil. That phenolic content was higher than that found in many vegetables, such as corn oil (1.87 mg/100g) and walnut oils (2.97mg/100g) (Gao et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2022). Fat-soluble antioxidants are present in different parts of freshwater fish species and have been mentioned in Table 2. Tocopherols are also present in different vegetable oils (Chen et al., 2011). In the present study, the content in *Cyprinus carpio* was 370.89 (mg/kg), which was higher than that found in *Labeo rohita* (354.23 mg/kg) and *Cirrhinus mrigala* (343.65 mg/kg). Our findings relate to the results of Zhang et al. (2020), which were observed in palm oil. Whereas plant sources such as walnut oil have 16.89 (mg/100g) and peanut oil have 14.37 (mg/100g) (Gao et al., 2018). Palm oil has tocopherol content in the range of 84.30 mg/kg, remarkably higher than found in tree seed oil (54.50 mg/100g) (Sun & Li 2016; Tokur el al., 2006). Tocopherol plays a vital role in providing higher antioxidant activity (Santos et al., 2018).

The fish oil fatty acid composition for different parts of freshwater fish species is summarized in Table 3. A significant portion of fatty acids was unsaturated fatty acids. In the present study, unsaturated fatty acid content (29-33%) was higher in *Labeo rohita* compared to the other two species. Saturated fatty acid content was higher in *Cirrhinus mrigala*. It ranged from 34-43%. The major saturated fatty acid was palmitic acid. Zuta et al. (2003), reported that palmitic acid was a dominant fatty acid in the head and visceral organs. Our findings also relate to the findings of Zuta et al. (2003), which were observed in soybean oil content. Polyunsaturated fatty acids are majorly beneficial in terms of human health (Chantachumz et al., 2000). Different factors, such as fish habitat, food, age, sex, place of development, and temperature, influence the content of fatty acids in fish species (Suseno et al., 2010). Myristic acid was found in the range of 6.30 ± 0.11 in the head region of *Labeo rohita*. It was higher compared to the other two fish species. Our findings relate to the results of Alasalvar et al. (2002), which were observed in buana cone liver oil. Palmitoleic acid was higher in the head region of *Cirrhinus mrigala* compared to other fish species (Kris et al., 2002). It was in the range of 2.23 ± 0.01 . Palmitic acid was higher in the head region of *Cirrhinus mrigala*. It was in the range of 13.5 ± 0.03 . Buana cone liver contained fatty acid were: oleic acid 15.86%, palmitic acid 13.65%, DHA 15.45%, with total Polyunsaturated fatty acid 18.11%, saturated fatty acids 17.76%, and monounsaturated fatty acids 23, 45% respectively. Alasalvar et al. (2002) reported that margaric acid was 3.05 ± 0.01 in the liver of both *Cyprinus carpio* and *Labeo rohita* (Tokur et al., 2006). Lauric acid was found in higher amounts in the head region of *Cyprinus carpio*. It was found in the range of 6.00 ± 0.02 . Capric acid was higher in the liver of *Cirrhinus mrigala*. It was in the range of 2.66 ± 0.09 (Rasoarahona et al., 2004). The amount of oleic acid was the same in the head region of all the fish samples. It was in the range of 3.11 ± 0.05 . Our findings relate to the results of Alasalvar et al. (2002), which were observed in sea bass. But the amount was different in other parts of all the samples. Deep-sea fish species contained dominant fatty acids such as palmitic acid and oleic acid with polyunsaturated fatty acids (5.11-89,54mg/g), monounsaturated fatty acids (63mg/g), and saturated fatty acids (15.11 mg/g). The difference in these fatty acids is due to the different feeding habitats of fish species (Suseno et al., 2010).

The purpose of this study was to find a simple and accurate method for the extraction and purification of squalene from fish processing waste. The method applied in this study has various advantages over those reported in the literature (Ragasa et al., 2015). The HPLC technique was used for the determination of squalene by using a mixture of acetonitrile and acetone as a mobile phase. These findings agree with the results of Hadinto et al. (2020), which report the content of squalene in olive oil using a mixture of acetone and acetonitrile. Squalene and cholesterol were the main compounds of the crude extract, and both of them

were triterpenes Ragasa et al., 2015). Fractional crystallization was done for the purification of squalene. Absolute ethanol was used in this technique to separate the compound. A mixture of acetone and methanol (3:7 vol/vol) was used in fractional crystallization (Hadinto et al., 2020). This method is simple and quick compared to the classic saponification method. For the analysis of squalene extracted from other sources apart from fish parts, this method can also be applied. A mixture of acetone and acetonitrile was used for HPLC analysis of squalene in olive oil (Hadinto et al., 2020). Low sensitivity was detected by using acetone for the separation of squalene (Lu et al., 2003). High sensitivity was detected by using methanol as a mobile phase (Spanggord et al., 2002). These results agree with observations carried out by (FAO, 2011) on the extraction of squalene from Amaranth seeds by using different solvents.

The content of squalene in different parts of freshwater fish species such as *Labeo rohita*, *Cirrhinus mrigala* and *Cyprinus carpio* has been illustrated in Fig 2. In *Labeo rohita*, the content of squalene in all analyzed parts ranged from 1.00 to 3.02 g/100g. Combined waste (3.02 ± 0.26 g/100g) was the most abundant source of squalene in *Labeo rohita* (Xiao et al., 2016). Our findings agree with the outcomes of Tan et al. (2007), which were observed in camellia oil. The content of squalene in the liver of *Labeo rohita* was 1.00 ± 0.02 . Our findings agree with the results of Gao et al. (2018), which were observed in olive oil. Content of squalene in the head region of *Labeo rohita* was $2.24.00 \pm 0.03$. In *Cyprinus carpio*, the content of squalene in all analyzed parts ranged from 2.65 to 3.76g/100g. Combined waste (3.76 ± 0.98 g/100g) was the most abundant source of squalene in *Cyprinus carpio* (Tan et al., 2007). The content of squalene in the liver of *Cyprinus carpio* was 3.06 ± 0.76 . Content of squalene in the head region of *Cyprinus carpio* was $2.65.0 \pm 0.45$. In *Cirrhinus mrigala*, the content of squalene in all analyzed parts ranged from 1.65 to 2.00 g/100g. Combined waste (2.00 ± 0.04 g/100g) was the most abundant source of squalene in *Cirrhinus mrigala*. The content of squalene in the liver of *Cirrhinus mrigala* was 1.65 ± 0.04 . Content of squalene in the head region of *Cirrhinus mrigala* was $1.98.00 \pm 0.05$. Olive oil has squalene content in the range of 92-96 mg/100g (Gao et al., 2018), but it was higher than that found in palm oil (52-58 mg/100g) and peanut oil (20-22 mg/100g) (Zhang et al., 2020).

The percentage purity of squalene obtained by the utilization of different parts of freshwater fish species has been illustrated in Fig 1. Maximum purity of squalene was detected in the head portion of freshwater fish species. The highest purity (97%) of squalene was detected in the head portion of *Cyprinus carpio*. It was the highest % when compared to other ratios (Fabia et al., 2009). *Cirrhinus mrigala* has 95%, and *Labeo rohita* has 96% purity of squalene in the head portion. In Table 4, properties of squalene, such as molecular weight, melting point, viscosity, boiling point, iodine number, and refractive index, are

summarized. The boiling point was 284 °C, which depends on the length of the carbon chain in oils (Chantachumz et al., 2000). Molecular weight was 408.7 g/mol, and viscosity was 12. All of these values meet the specified quality standards.

Acid values and peroxide values of the squalene extracted from freshwater fish species are shown in Fig 3. The acid values of *Labeo rohita*, *Cirrhinus mrigala*, and *Cyprinus carpio* were 28.43, 30.18, and 31.11 (mg KOH/g), respectively. Our findings agree with the results of Chantachumz et al. (2000). Peroxide values of the above species were 7.99, 7.76, and 8.67 (mEQ/L). Peroxide value is an indication of auto-oxidation. Peroxide value and acid value of mackerel byproducts were 3.3-3.6 (mEQ/kg) and 4-5 mg/g, respectively (Zuta et al., 2003). Our results agree with the findings of Chantachumz et al. (2000), observed in mackerel. The variations that exist among all freshwater fish species depend upon the non-homogeneous nature of fish processing waste, different batches of fish, and physiological variations of fish (Chantachumz et al., 2000).

Conclusion

The fish discards produced during fish processing create massive economic loss and serious environmental problems. It is estimated that about two-thirds of the total amount of fish is discarded as waste material. Extraction and purification of squalene from different fish discards is an excellent approach to overcome this problem. This study concludes that the fractional crystallization method effectively extracts and purifies squalene, offering a sustainable technique that supports marine conservation by reducing dependency on shark-derived resources. HPLC technology gave us significantly more reliable results compared to other methods. This single-step approach is superior in terms of squalene purity and yield compared to other methods. Using these techniques, fish processing waste could be utilized to extract squalene instead of hunting sea sharks. In this way, marine life will be protected. Hence, the proposed approach provides a sustainable and cost-effective method for obtaining squalene from fish processing waste.

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